

EVALUATION OF EXPERT SYSTEMS (HOMOEOPATHIC) BY DELONE AND MCLEAN MODEL OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS: A CASE STUDY OF SINDH PROVINCE, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Evaluation of systems is very important for the performance improvement of systems. There is a lack of studies on Homeopathic Expert Systems evaluation. Therefore, the current study evaluates the Homeopathic Expert Systems under use by Homeopathic doctors practicing in Sindh Province of Pakistan. This research employed the quantitative methodology to administer questionnaires to Homoeopathic Doctors using expert systems in Sindh Province (Hyderabad, Karachi, and Mirpurkhas Divisions), Pakistan. The data were analyzed through structural equation modeling, including testing the hypotheses. The results indicate that Information Quality, System Quality, and Service Quality positively and significantly influence User Satisfaction. Similarly, the effect of User Satisfaction on Net Benefit was also found significantly positive. These results show that Homoeopathic expert systems users expect that their systems must be of high-quality and provide high-quality information and services along with significant user benefits. Overall, the findings emanating from the current research support the DeLone-McLean model completely as a predictive model. This research enriches our understanding of information systems' effectiveness based on DeLone and McLean's model of information system success. The findings reveal a significant statistical relationship between the proposed variables in the context of Homoeopathy expert systems. Further, the study outlines an evaluation procedure for Homoeopathic expert systems, which previous studies have not done before. Additionally, this research concludes Pakistani Homoeopathic Doctors using Expert systems and provides practitioners with practical recommendations that will bring possible and realistic benefits. Another contribution of the thesis lies in the context of the research. Particularly, this research is the first of its kind conducted in Pakistan; before this study, the research on the evaluation of Expert Systems (Homeopathic) in Pakistan was not conducted.

Keywords: DeLone and McLean, evaluation, Homoeopathic, and expert system

INTRODUCTION

The field of information systems (iss) initially received attention from research scholars in the 1960s (langerfors, 1966), intending to design and implement data processing applications (avgerou, 2000). Is research has been evolved from well-developed disciplines Such as operational research, computer science, organizational behavior, and management.

However, despite significant research implications to support the organizational process changes, information systems could not emerge as an individual discipline. To support the deep understanding of information systems, analysis, empirical models, and conceptual research is required to a larger extent (irani, gunasekaran & love, 2006). Irani, gunasekaran & love (2006)

stressed that information systems had a major influence on all society sectors, which includes health care and education.

Several research scholars have examined the topic of evaluation of information systems. However, the research in this field is extensive and diverse, as it contains different approaches and models (häkkinen and hilmola, 2008; rai and lang, 2002; seddon 1997; markus and tanis 2000; nah & kuang, 2001; seddon & kew 1997; goodhue & thompson 1995; irani, gunasekaran & love, 2006; rokyia & meriouh 2015; Adroni & Sitorus, 2017). However, the literature regarding the evaluation of Expert Systems (Homeopathic) is very scarce, particularly in developing countries like Pakistan. Many patients are diverting their focus on homeopathic treatment instead of allopathic due to many reasons. For instance, homeopathic remedy does not involve any side effects or risks. In contrast, if the examination is not done well in allopathic treatment, and all other factors have not been considered relevant to the systems and disease, the prescribed medicine may have adverse effects to a greater extent. As a result, the Homeopathic doctors have seen a surge in the number of patients which has increased the burden as well. Consequently, many homeopaths have started using several Expert Systems (Homeopathy) to help them in diagnosis and prescribing proper medications. However, to what extent these expert systems (Homeopathy) are working accurately is relatively unknown and to what extent the users (homeopathic doctors) are satisfied with the performance of these expert systems is also not known. Hence, it merits consideration and needs further investigation. This study particularly aims to fill these literature gaps.

This study offers several significant theoretical and practical contributions: primarily, the research enriches the literature in terms of describing the evaluation system of Expert Systems (Homeopathic). Secondly, the study presents system performance data and the experience of implementing the Expert system (Homeopathic). The third contribution of the research is that it indicates the underlying factors for the relative success of the execution of the expert system (Homeopathic). The fourth contribution of the current research lies in the context of the study. Notably, this research is the first of its kind to be conducted in Pakistan; before this study, no research was conducted in Pakistan that focuses on

the evaluation of Expert Systems (Homeopathic). In addition, this study describes and discusses several issues arising from the implementation of information systems and delivers beneficial recommendations on the options or practices required to obtain benefits in applying information systems.

2. Theoretical framework and hypotheses development

2.1 Why Homoeopathic doctors need an Expert System?

It has been argued that most clinical errors were due to oversight, as without considering all possibilities, they played an essential role in determining the patient's access to appropriate diagnosis and treatment (Ladley Adels and Greed, 1979). Therefore, doctors need help to determine the proper diagnosis and treatment, especially when a particular disease or the symptoms of a patient lead to diverse interpretations. Given that all the requisite information related to the patient, including history and details of symptoms, could be saved and classified in a computer system. In such a situation, a computer system could be more useful, fast, and accurate in terms of a detailed response than a common practitioner (Barr & Feigenbaum, 1982). When an expert doctor provides detailed information about the illness and symptoms that are then stored in the expert system so that whenever needed the system can interpret and suggest proper remedy based on the matching symptoms of patient and treatment already stored in the system.

A comprehensive and satisfactory examination of the patient relies on the Homeopathic doctor's skills and ability to identify, store, record, reference, analyze or evaluate any category or dataset. This needs a classification system that standardizes and encodes concepts and related information for easy use.

2.2 Expert System and Homoeopathy

The introduction of Expert Systems in the examination and treatment of patients has done away with early skepticism, and expanded its application, for instance, KARDIO (Bratko, 1989), NESTOR (Cooper, 1984), CASNET (Kulikowski & Weiss, 1982), ATTENDING (Miller, 1988), SAM (Gascuel, 1981), CENTAURI (Aikins, 1980), DIGITALIS THERAPY ADVISOR (Gorry et al., 1978), PIP (Pauker & Szolovitz, 1977),

INTERNIST (Pople, 1977), TEIREISIAS (Davis, 1976), and MYCIN (Shortliffe, 1976) are some of its examples. Regrettably, despite the development of computer systems based on this alternative medicine, only the following few expert systems have received recognition:

- **RADAR** is one of the famous homeopathic expert systems widely used globally (Shrogens, 1982). The system comprises numerous pharmacopeias, including those by Allen, Hering, Heneman, and Boerick. Particularly, RADAR cover up to 2000 remedies and their respective pharmacopeias.

- **HINEIRO** is also a very commonly used expert system that covers 2535 Boenninghausen therapy rubrics (symptoms) (Bachelerie, 1986). Every therapeutic rubric is linked with the widely used remedies.

- **ABIES** is another expert system that helps Homeopaths find suitable remedies based on the law of Similars (Benson, 1980). Besides providing proper medications, this system offers patient's treatment history and notes based on the Real Clinical Classification (RCC) system. The RCC system is based on the hierarchical classification of nomenclature into four levels (Read & Benson, 1986), which helps the doctors.

STAPHISE is another type of Homeopathic expert system which is based on the Ken repertory. The system is comprised of 20000 rubrics created through different pharmacopoeias. Another added benefit of STAPHISE is that its database is customizable (Salaijn & Simonet, 1989).

Homeopathic medicine is grounded on the stimulation of an organism's healing system by supplying certain homeopathic dilutions consistent with specific amounts of the medications (F. ALONSO-AMO 1995). Homeopathy is a system of medicines through which Homeopaths/ Homeopathic Doctors provide treatment to individuals according to the symptoms. Furthermore, in Homeopathy, the medicines are prescribed according to patients' symptoms, which vary from patient to patient. Hence, the medication for each patient will be different for the same disease/ problem. It is difficult to choose proper medicines for a new homeopathic doctor. Computer models that are applied to simulate medical decision-making are mostly based on probability methodology (Gorry, Silverman, & Pauker, 1978; Solomon & Papert, 1976). Despite impressive results provided by these

programs, doctors cannot identify proper diagnosis and raises questions about the over-diagnosis quality proposed. Nowadays, there are several homeopathic expert systems available to help the homeopaths for selecting the remedies according to symptoms such as Radar, Cara, and Homeopathic Repertory. Even in some cases, unique expert systems are also available for a particular treatment of some significant diseases, such as for the treatment of glaucoma "Expert System for Homeopathic Glaucoma Treatment" is one of the potential systems (Alonso-Amo 1995).

2.3 Homeopathy

The Homeopathy was founded by German physician Dr. Samuel Christian Hahnemann (Ahsan Shafi Memon 2020; De Schepper, 2011). Homeopathy is a way of alternative treatment where the Homeopathic Doctors (Homeopaths) treat the patients according to the symptoms and the prescribed homeopathic medicines, which can be different for every patient for the same problem/disease. It depends on the symptoms, clinical trial previously done, and preserved in the *Materia Medica* (Book of Homeopathic Medicines) (Owen, 2015). The treatment primarily focused on the general symptoms and history of the respective patient and is a popular alternative way of treatment besides allopathic. The Homeopathic treatment aimed to activate the healing mechanism of organs by providing diluted medicines with particular medicines. In this way the patient regain health completely after eradication of symptoms and signs from which the patient is suffering. The Homeopathic treatment system besides treating disease also addresses the causes of disease and respective patient's susceptibility.

2.3.1 Principles of Homeopathy

One of Homeopathy's fundamental principles is the "Law of Similars," which is based on symptomatic treatment. It is also known as the law of Similia, which means that "like cures like." (Ahsan Shafi Memon 2020). In other words, when a healthy person takes medicine or substance, such substance produces certain types of symptoms. Similarly, an unhealthy person can be cured through a substance that produces the same symptoms experienced by the unhealthy (Ahsan Shafi Memon et al 2018; Ahsan Shafi Memon, 2020; De Schepper, 2010). To put it simply, an ill patient can be treated through a substance that also

produces similar symptoms (Lockie A. 2000, p.10). It means that homeopathy improves the vital force/immune system against the symptoms produced in a homeopathic way and cure the disease related to such symptoms. This principle is based on the remedy that best matches the symptoms of an unhealthy person. Although the medicines are helpful to cure a disease, an individual's power of healing is also necessary. For instance, the Greek Physician Hippocrates in the 5th Century BC also anticipated that patients should be encouraged to believe in their healing power to cure a disease (Lockie A. 2000, p.10).

2.3.2 Homeopathic simillimum

The Simillimum is one of the primary Homoeopathic remedies, which is unique and covers all the symptoms being faced by the patient under treatment (Kayne, 2008).

2.3.3 Individualized homoeopathic treatment

The individualized homoeopathic remedy is a kind of distinctive treatment based on the basic principles of Homoeopathy given to the patients based on their symptoms very closely matching the signs of the remedy/ medicines (Ahsan Shafi Memon et al. 2018; Kayne, 2008). Besides matching the symptoms, this type of remedies also pay close attention to other general characteristics of the patients, including perspiration, sleep, appetite, and energy.

2.3.4 Potentization

Bloch & Lewis (2003) argue that potentization refers to the process of diluting and shaking a substance. It is also known as "dynamization."

2.3.5 *Materia medica*

In the Homoeopathic medicine system, the 'Materia Medica' is a Book, which comprises detailed information about each homoeopathic remedy's symptoms. The book is based on extensive research and numerous clinical trials (Ahsan Shafi Memon et al. 2018; Owen, 2015).

2.3.6 Repertory

Like in every book, there is an index at the beginning of the book, which indicates the respective list of every topic covered. Similarly, the 'Repertory' is like an index, which records all the symptoms along with a list conforming to each

symptom related to a specific remedy (Kayne & Kayne, 2007; Owen, 2015).

2.3.7 Individualized homoeopathic treatment

The individualized homoeopathic treatment begins by intensely interviewing the patient, which considers the detailed history of the patient's illness, including the individual's mental, psychological, and physical symptoms. This method is fundamental in the Homoeopathic medicine system because it helps collect important information about the patient, which is essential in prescribing suitable remedies (Kayne & Kayne, 2007; Owen, 2015; De Schepper, 2010). The details of the patient's condition and symptoms help a doctor to find a treatment based on the law of similars (Verhoef et al., 2005; 2002; Owen, 2015; Eyles, Leydon, Lewith, & Brien, 2011; De Schepper, 2010; Subramanian & Subramanian, 2004). This procedure is then followed by analyzing the case and through manual or computerized repertorization (De Schepper, 2010; Bloch & Lewis, 2003; Van Dulmen & Bensing; Watson, 2009). The Repertory provides a list of remedies (Kayne & Kayne, 2007; Owen, 2015). Subsequently, the medication that best meets the patient's symptoms and other characteristics are selected for the patient's treatment (Kayne, 2007; Owen, 2015; Bloch & Lewis, 2003). Homoeopathic medicine is also very well recognized for avoiding eating disorders (Ahsan Shafi Memon et al. 2018; Dehn, 2012). Furthermore, besides treating the illness, there are numerous benefits to choosing Homoeopathic treatment. For instance, in the case of persons with binge eating habits, the benefits include:

- Homoeopathy is itself a therapeutic treatment by nature (Dehn, 2012; Brien et al., 2011).
- The doctor-patient relationship may help to encourage and enable the patient to continue treatment
- This type of remedy aims to provide patients with comprehensive psychological, emotional and physical therapy while also considering other factors and causes (Brien et al. 2011).

2.4 Information Systems Model of DeLone and McLean

DeLeon and McLean's theory on information systems' success strives for a comprehensive

understanding of the information system's success (DeLon and McLean, 1992; DeLone and McLean, 2003). This theory links the most important aspects of success, usually the evaluation, description, and interpretation of information systems.

2.4.1 Previous model for the success of Information systems proposed by DeLone and McLean (1992)

Initially, DeLone and McLean proposed a model for evaluating the Information System's success in 1992 (DeLon and McLean, 1992). Compared to other studies published before 1992, their model had some advantages in measuring the success of the whole information system or a part/component of the full system, which previous studies neglected in the past. DeLone and McLean outlined a comprehensive, multidimensional model of Information System success (1992). This model acts as a framework to gauge dependent variables in Information System Research. Relying on several studies, the Information System has been classified into the following six dimensions (Figure 1):

- System quality
- Information quality
- Use
- User satisfaction
- Individual impact
- Organizational Impact

Figure 1. The previous Model of success of Information Systems proposed DeLone and McLean (Source: DeLone and McLean 1992, p.87)

2.4.2 Updated Information system's success model proposed by DeLone and McLean in 2003

The updated and revised model of information system's success proposed by DeLone and McLean in 2003 shows the interconnection between six interdependent factors: information quality, system quality, service quality, use or intention to use, and user satisfaction and net benefits. Since the study proposing a revised model has been cited by more than 300 scholars globally, it shows that the model is very successful and reliable, as argued by Heo and Han (2003). According to the recent details, more than 3400 research scholars worldwide have cited their study. Therefore, the updated model of the information system's success has been adopted in the current research.

The above 1992 model was revised by incorporating service quality as a third quality factor; moreover, organizational impact and individual impact were substituted with net benefits (DeLone and McLean 2003; DeLone and McLean 1992). There is a correlation between user satisfaction, intention to use, and use (Petter *et al.* 2008; DeLone and McLean 2003; DeLone and McLean 1992). Figure 2 represents the updated model of the information system's success proposed by DeLone and McLean in 2003.

Figure 2. The updated model of Information System's success proposed by DeLone and McLean in 2003

(Source: DeLone and McLean 2003, p.24)

2.5 Dimension of Information System Success

2.5.1 Information Quality

It is described as the essential information features that the Information System generates. The information quality is vital for the satisfaction of end-users (Petter et al. 2008, Bharati and Berg 2005), as it determines users' satisfaction to resolve their tasks. Hence, in the case of bad information quality, it will be difficult to understand the information and will have an adverse impression among users (Allwood 1998). Information quality components are the format of the information, timeliness, relevancy, completeness, and accuracy (Petter et al. (2008).

2.5.2 System Quality

Usually, it is related to the overall performance of the Information System (Bharati and Chaudhury, 2004). Notably, it is defined as the desired features of an Information System used by decision-makers and users (DeLone and McLean 1992). Essential elements of system quality include ease of use, the flexibility of system, and ease of learning (Bharati and Berg 2005; Petter et al. (2008). The above components of system quality enable users to put less effort into accessing information; moreover, users' effortless information is more acceptable (Davis 1989; Rivard et al. 1997). In addition, the ease of use increases the Information System's efficiency (Doll and Torkzadeh 1988).

2.5.3 Service Quality

The service quality is described as the general support provided by service providers to users (DeLone and McLean 2003; Petter et al. 2008). Important components of Service Quality are empathy, reliability, assurance, and responsiveness (Bharati and Berg 2005; DeLone and McLean 2003; Petter et al. 2008). These components together improve the service quality of Information Systems. Empathy helps to understand the specific needs of users (Jiang et al. 2002). Reliability is the dependability of users, and hence, the organizations should fulfill their promises regarding the provision of services (Jiang et al. 2002, Pitt et al. 1995). Responsiveness is related to help users whenever they need without any delay (Jiang et al. 2002). In comparison, Assurance is related to solving user problems by the support unit. Moreover, it has been argued that the

service quality should also contain user's systems knowledge by incorporating system understanding and training (Bailey and Pearson 1983; Li 1997; Magal 1991; Ives et al. 1983) since these

Table 1 Dimensions of information success model components can reduce user dependence on support units and enhance the satisfaction of users.

25.4 Use

The Information System Use has many aspects and is a complex dimension (DeLone and McLean 2003; DeLone and McLean 1992). Seddon (1997) defined the use as the efforts to consume the Information System Use. In contrast, DeLone and McLean (1992) pointed out that when use is voluntary, practical use as a method to evaluate information. Similarly, Rai et al. (2002) emphasized that an excellent model to assess the use is via determining the utilization of Information System.

2.5.5 User Satisfaction

It is one of the measures of the Information System's success (Raymond 1990; DeLone and McLean 2003; Bailey and Person 1983). It is referred to as the response of users towards satisfaction for using Information System (DeLone and McLean 1992). In the previous DeLone and McLean's model, it was measured via information quality and system quality (DeLone and McLean 1992; Rai et al. 2002). Furthermore, in order to assess user satisfaction, a single measure can be used as proposed by Baroudi and Orlikowski (1988).

2.5.6 Net Benefits

The organizational effect and individual effect were substituted with net benefits in the revised model of DeLone and McLean (DeLone and McLean 2003) because the effect can be either negative or positive. However, the net benefits can cover both of these attributes. Furthermore, the benefits of using Information System has been classified into 04 types: customer satisfaction, management control, task innovation, and task productivity, as proposed by Torkzadeh and Doll (1999). Table 1 represents all the dimensions of the Information success model based on the DeLone and McLean model of 2003.

Information Quality	System Quality	Service Quality	User Satisfaction	Net benefits
Information accuracy	Ease of use	Understanding	One dimension (4 indicators)	Task productivity
Completeness	Ease of learning	Training		Task innovation
Timeliness		Reliability		Customer satisfaction
Format		Responsiveness		Management control
Relevancy		Assurance Empathy		

2.6 Information System Evaluation

The Information Systems provides timely, reliable, and accurate information (Elpez and Fink 2006). The organizations use these systems at different levels to transform and sort out data into a more meaningful form to make decisions. There are several sub-systems of Information Systems categorized by functional or organizational limitations. For instance, a special sub-system for the market forecast or inventory control (Ives *et al.* 1980); moreover, the information from the information system can be provided at different intervals (Senn (1978). Based on previous research, DeLone and McLean proposed a logical grouping of measures and attempted to propose six dimensions of Information System Success (Sedera and Gable 2004), their 02 contributions were based on the model proposed by Seddon and Kiew (1996). The Information System success model presented by DeLone and McLean is an important and highly cited model that received significant attention from research scholars and practitioners globally since 1992 (Petter and McLean 2009, Al-adaileh 2009). Furthermore, compared to other studies, the DeLone and McLean model is advantageous in measuring either the success of the whole information system or a part of the complete information system, which previous studies neglected in the past (DeLone and McLean 2003). Moreover, it is also appropriate to assess the success of the Information System in private and public sectors (See, for instance, Elpez and Fink 2006; Almutairi and Subramanian 2005).

Due to uncertainty, many organizations are interested in evaluating the Information System investment (Skok *et al.* 2001; Lubbe and Remenyi 1999; Remenyi and Sherwood-Smith 1999). Such interest in assessing the Information System investment has increased because of the investments made by the organizations (Fitzgerald 1998).

There is a lot of work done in expert systems of other fields, but few researchers have worked in homoeopathic expert system. Alonso-Amo *et al.*'s (1994) study revealed how Expert System works and helps the homoeopaths treat the patients of Glaucoma by Homoeopathic treatment with the SEHO expert's help system. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a study on the evaluation of Expert Systems (Homoeopathic).

2.7 Hypotheses Development

Based on the DeLone and McLean (2003) study, the current thesis presents a multidimensional model for the success of an Expert System (Homeopathy). The proposed model is grounded on five interconnected constructs, i.e., information quality, system quality, service quality, user satisfaction, and net benefits in the context of Homeopathy Expert systems. DeLone and McLean (2003), in their research, find that the overall quality of the information system is based on three factors, namely, information quality, system quality, and service quality; these three factors significantly impact the user satisfaction, and the user satisfaction in turn significantly influences the net benefits. Hence, this study proposes the following hypotheses:

H1: Information quality of the expert system (Homoeopathy) is significantly and positively related to user satisfaction.

H2: System quality of the expert system (Homoeopathy) is significantly and positively related to user satisfaction.

H3: Service quality of the expert system (Homoeopathy) is significantly and positively related to user satisfaction.

H4: User satisfaction significantly and positively related to Net benefits of an expert system (Homoeopathy).

The hypothesized research model is represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Hypothesized Research Model 3. Research Methods

Several researchers have adopted and validated DeLone and McLean's model through empirical studies and provided different implications for theory and practice in different contexts

(Häkkinen and Hilmola, 2008; Rai and Lang, 2002; Seddon 1997; Markus and Tanis 2000; Nah & Kuang, 2001; Seddon & Kew 1997; Goodhue & Thompson 1995; Irani, Gunasekaran & Love, 2006; Rokya & Meriouh 2015; Adroni & Sitorus, 2017). Since the updated DeLone and McLean's model of the IS success is one of the commonly used and highly cited models, therefore, it was decided to choose this model to assess the success of Homeopathic Expert System (DeLon & McLean 2003).

The updated and revised DeLon & McLean's model proposes that information systems' success is based on seven factors: information quality, system quality, service quality, use, intention to use, user satisfaction, and net benefits (DeLon & McLean 2003). The "intention to use" and "use" were not systematically examined because the current study focuses on evaluating the expert system in terms of its practical use; thus, the system's use is obligatory to assess its performance. Moreover, this study confined the sample criteria to at least 01-year practical use of Homeopathic Expert System.

3.1 Sample and data collection

This research employs the quantitative approach to administer questionnaires to users of Homeopathic Expert Systems of Sindh Province (Hyderabad, Karachi, and Mirpurkhas Divisions), Pakistan. Since the data regarding the use of Expert System (homeopathic) in Pakistan is not available, it was decided to personally visit the Homeopathic Clinics in-person to obtain the requisite data. The data was collected through a closed-ended questionnaire from respondents using any Homeopathic Expert System for at least 1 year. This study focused on the three most popular expert systems i.e. Radar, Cara, and Homeopathic Repertory. After obtaining demographic information, respondents were asked to indicate whether they are using any Homeopathic Expert System or otherwise. The respondents that were not using any Expert System were excluded from the study. Mainly, 228 Homeopathic doctors (who were using homeopathic Expert System) were

contacted to participate in the survey. However, after excluding 14 partially filled questionnaires, the total complete and valid sample size becomes 214, indicating a very high response rate (93.85%).

3.2 Measures

The development and selection of questionnaire items require a systematic balance between adhering to established standards and adapting those standards to current circumstances. Particular attention was paid to follow the definitions and standards set by DeLone and McLean (2003). Although the model was slightly modified to fit into the research objectives, the basic model and its dimensions are the same. The original questionnaire items would be considered effective and ensure greater acceptance; however, minor adjustments were made in the questionnaire items to fit into the research aims and improve their effectiveness. The questionnaire was divided into four parts. The first part obtained information about demographic details of respondents. In the second part, the participants were asked to provide some details about their use of Homeopathic Expert System. The third part acquired information about the measurement of Information Quality, System Quality, Service Quality, and Net Benefits. Finally, the last fourth part obtained details about measuring the User Satisfaction construct.

The *information quality* was assessed by adopting five factors suggested by Bharati and Chaudhury (2004), i.e., relevancy, format, timeliness, completeness, and information accuracy. Various scholars have also used these dimensions and found valid and reliable (See, for instance, Al-Adaileh 2009; Rai *et al.* 2002; Doll and Torkzadeh 1988; Bailey and Pearson 1983). Similarly, the *system quality* was measured by adopting two components, i.e., ease of learning and use as proposed by Rivard *et al.* (1997). These dimensions have also been used by various scholars and found valid and reliable (See, for instance, Seddon 1997; Doll and Torkzadeh 1988; Bharati and Chaudhury 2004; Petter *et al.* 2008).

Likewise, to assess the *service quality*, two components, namely training provided to the users and understanding of system as proposed by Li (1997) and four measures namely reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy proposed by

Pitt *et al.* (1995) have been adopted in this study. Previous studies have already validated these components (See, for instance, Parasuraman *et al.* 1988; Jiang *et al.* 2002; Van Dyke *et al.* 1997; Ives *et al.* 1983; Magal 1991; Bailey and Pearson 1983). Finally, to assess *user satisfaction*, the questions proposed by Seddon and Keiew (1996) has been used. Additionally, a new question was developed to measure patients' level of satisfaction from the treatment suggested by Homeopathic Expert System. This item was rated on a five-point Likert scale (Ranging from Very Dissatisfied = 1 to Very Satisfied = 5).

4. Results

4.1 Profile of respondents

The majority of respondents are Male representing 67.8%. In terms of age of the participants, most respondents fall within the 41-50 Years age group (42.5%) followed by 51 and above years old (22.9%), 31-35 years old (13.6%), 36-40 years old (10.3%), 26-30 years (7%) and 18-25 years old (3.7%). Further, the majority of respondents are using RADAR (43.5%) Homeopathic Expert System followed by CARA (30.3%), Homoeopathic Repertory (26.2%). These statistics indicate that most homoeopathic users in Sindh Province prefer to use RADAR, CARA, and Homoeopathic Repertory Homeopathic Expert Systems. **Table 2** shows the characteristics of the participants.

Table 2

Characteristics	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	145	67.8%
	Female	69	32.2%
Age	18-25 Years	8	3.7
	26-30 Years	15	7.0
	31-35 Years	29	13.6
	36-40 Years	22	10.3
	41-50 Years	91	42.5
	51 and above	49	22.9
Homeopathic Systems in use	Expert		
	RADAR	93	43.5%
	CARA	65	30.3%
	Homoeopathic Repertory	56	26.2%

Characteristics of the respondents (N= 214). Additionally, a new question was developed to measure patients' level of satisfaction from the treatment suggested by Homeopathic Expert System. This item was rated on a five-point Likert scale (Ranging from Very Dissatisfied=1 to Very Satisfied=5). The results reveal that over 48% of respondents rated the satisfaction level at 5 points out of the total 5 points, while over 25% of the participants rated the satisfaction level at 4 points. In other words, over 73% of respondents believe that patients are highly satisfied with the treatment suggested through the expert system. **Figure 4** represents the level of satisfaction.

Figure 4 Level of satisfaction of patients from the treatment suggested by Homeopathic Expert System.

4.2 Reliability and validity

Initially, the reliability and validity of the questionnaire were assessed through various statistical analysis techniques. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity were employed to see whether the appropriateness for conducting exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The questionnaire's KMO value was within the threshold limit (i.e., .747), and Bartlett's test of sphericity was also statistically significant, enabling good suitability for conducting EFA.

In employing EFA, it was decided to choose principal component factors and the varimax rotation method to determine whether the survey instrument (27 items) were corresponding to one or more factors or dimensions. Additionally, to ascertain the EFA results, two standard criteria were followed, i.e., eigenvalue must be equal to greater than 1 (one), and factor loadings must be equal or higher than 0.5. In total, 04 (four) items were removed from the final factor analysis since these questions failed to meet the EFA requirements.

The final factor structure (unrotated) indicated a total 07 (seven) factors. The eigenvalues and factor loadings of all factors were > 1.0 and ≥ 0.5 , respectively. The EFA results show that the total variance explained was 80.025%, which is excellent. The results further indicate that the Information Quality construct was composed of four (04) indicators, while the System Quality was comprised

of two (02) indicators. Similarly, Service Quality was composed of four (04) indicators, and User Satisfaction was comprised of three (03) indicators). Finally, the Net Benefits construct was composed of three factors, namely Task Productivity, Customer Satisfaction, and Management Control, with each having three (03) individual indicators. The detail of EFA analysis results are presented in **Table 3**.

Further, CFA was also used to assess the discriminant validity of constructs. In doing so, the nested model approach, along with the chi-square difference test, was used. The results reveal that the five-factor model proposed in this study has much better model indices ($\chi^2 = 185.875$, $df = 111$, CFI = 0.968, TLI = 0.961, RSMEA = 0.056) and these results show that the data fits well as compared with other competing models. These model indices results are also in line with the recommended criteria proposed by Chau (1997), which confirms the discriminant validity. The CFA analysis results are presented in **Table 4**.

Furthermore, the average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) tests were also conducted to examine the convergent validity and construct reliability. The data analysis results reveal that the value of AVE and CR were higher than the minimum value for both tests (> 0.5 and > 0.7 , respectively) (Podsakoff et al. 2003). Mainly, the AVE values ranged between 0.606 to 0.802. Similarly, the values of CR ranged between 0.822 to 0.948, thus confirming the convergent validity and construct

reliability. **Table 3** summarizes the CR and AVE results. Moreover, the value of Cronbach Alpha of Questionnaire was .841, which is excellent. Similarly, the Cronbach alpha value of each construct range between .784 to .965. These results show that the reliability of the questionnaire is excellent. Additionally, to further examine the discriminant validity, the AVE's square root for each construct was compared with the correlation between constructs with other constructs. The results indicate that the square root of AVE is greater than the correlation of corresponding constructs. Thus, convergent validity can be confirmed.

4.3 Common Method Bias

The existence of common method bias (CMB) was evaluated through Harman's single-factor test following the guidelines proposed by Podsakoff et al. (2003). For this purpose, EFA was employed, including all variables. The results show that the first dimension was only accounted for 23.775% of the total variance that the data must not be affected by CMB as the factor variance was less than 50% (Podsakoff MacKenzie, Lee, & Podsakoff, 2003).Table 3

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Construct/ Variable	Items	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	AVE	CR	
Information Quality	Information accuracy	The information in this System is accurate	.785	.885	0.725	0.913
	Completeness	This System provides sufficient information	.875			
	Timeliness	The information in this System is up-to-date	.892			
	Format	The information in this System is presented in a clear way	.851			
System Quality	Ease of use	This System is easy to use	.937	.965	0.802	0.948
	Ease of learning	This System is easy to learn	.962			
Service Quality	Understanding	I have sufficient understanding about this System	.731	.880	0.646	0.901
	Reliability	If the Service Support promises to do something by a certain time they will	.875			
	Responsiveness	The Service Support provide prompt service	.867			
	Assurance	The Service Support has adequate knowledge to help me if I experience any problems with this System	.818			
	Empathy	The Service Support understands my needs	.713			
User Satisfaction		How adequately do you feel that the system meets the information processing needs of your area of responsibility?	.822	.923	0.751	0.900
		How efficient is the system?	.898			
		Overall, are you satisfied with the system?	.878			
Net benefits	Task productivity:	This System allows me to accomplish more work than would otherwise be possible.	.819	.898	0.743	0.896
		This System increases my productivity	.873			
		This System application saves my time	.892			
Customer satisfaction:		This System helps me meet customer needs	.790	.894	0.747	0.898
		This System improves customer satisfaction	.879			

	This System improves customer service	.919				
Management control:	This system helps the management to control the work process	.780				
	This System improves management control.	.799	.784	0.606	0.822	
	This System helps management control performance	.755				

Notes: Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

Table 4

Chi-square difference test and nested model comparison

CFA models	χ^2	df	$\Delta \chi^2$ from model 1	RMSEA	IFI	TLI	CFI
Five-factor model	185.875	111		.056	.969	.961	.968
Four-factor model	209.115	112	23.241***	.064	.960	.950	.959
Three-factor model	226.382	113	40.508***	.069	.953	.943	.952
Two-factor model	269.402	114	83.528***	.080	.935	.922	.935
One-factor model	193.560	114	7.686***	.063	.962	.952	.961

*** $p < 0.001$

4.4 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics, including correlation, are presented in **Table 5**. The results show that all the independent variables are positively related to the dependent variables. Additionally, all the significant correlations' coefficient is less than .50; hence, there is no multicollinearity issue. Particularly, the results indicate that the Pearson correlation coefficient between Service Quality and User Satisfaction ($r = .469$) was higher than System Quality ($r = .331$) and Information Quality ($r = .257$). Further, the correlation coefficient between User Satisfaction and three dimensions of Net Benefit was also positive and significant.

Table 5
Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Information Quality	3.81	0.96	0.851						
System Quality	3.98	0.96	0.055	0.896					
Service Quality	3.49	1.01	0.027	.220**	0.804				
User Satisfaction	4.05	0.92	.257**	.331**	.469**	0.867			
Task Productivity	4.38	0.73	0.132**	0.092	0.121**	0.067	0.862		
Customer Satisfaction	4.47	0.66	0.131**	0.124**	0.13**	0.121**	.469**	0.864	
Management Control	4.38	0.68	.271**	0.05	0.15**	.237**	.477**	.415**	0.778

Notes: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The values on off diagonal in bold indicates the square root of AVE

4.5 Hypotheses Testing

Following the previous studies (Rokya & Meriouh 2015; Adroni & Sitorus, 2017), Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique was employed to test the hypotheses because it enables to estimate interrelations of several constructs simultaneously and control measurement errors. SEM is a multivariate data analysis tool, especially to assess the causal relationship between variables (Latan & Gudono, 2012). The model indices were within the commonly allowed limit. In other words, the data shows that the proposed model has significantly good fit indices ($\chi^2 = 185.875$, $df = 111$, goodness-of-fit statistic [GFI] = 0.906, comparative fit index [CFI] = 0.968, Tucker-Lewis index [TLI] = 0.961, root mean square error of approximation [RMSEA] = 0.056). Based on these results, SEM can be used for testing the hypotheses.

The hypothesis H1 proposes that Information Quality positively and significantly affects the User Satisfaction. The data analysis results reveal a significantly positive impact of Information Quality on User Satisfaction ($\beta = .302$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, in hypothesis H2, it was proposed that System Quality has a positive and significant impact on User Satisfaction. The results indicate that the impact of System Quality on User Satisfaction is positive and significant ($\beta = .223$, $p < 0.001$). Likewise, in hypothesis H3, it was proposed that Service Quality has a positive and significant impact on User Satisfaction. The results show that positive and significant effect of Service Quality on User Satisfaction ($\beta = .386$, $p < 0.001$). Correspondingly, in hypothesis H4, it was proposed that User Satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on Net Benefits. The results indicate that the impact of System Quality on User Satisfaction is positive and significant ($\beta = .250$, $p < 0.01$). From the above results, all four proposed hypotheses have been accepted. The SEM results are represented in Figure 5 and Table 6.

Additional explanation of the contribution values of the comprehensive factors of Net benefits (latent variable) demonstrates that Task Productivity, with a value of 0.70, can largely explain Net Benefits followed by Management Control (0.68) and Customer Satisfaction (0.64). Therefore, Task Productivity is the most crucial factor for Net Benefits, which implies that Homeopathic Doctors must pay more attention to Task Productivity.

Figure 5. Results of Structural Equation Modeling

Table 6
Structural Equation Modelling results

Hypothesis	Path	Estimate	<i>p</i>	Results
H1	Information Quality → User	.302	***	Accepted
H2	System Quality → User	.223	***	Accepted
H3	Service Quality → User	.386	***	Accepted
H4	User Satisfaction → Net	.250	**	Accepted

Note: ****p* < 0.001; ***p* < 0.01

4.6 Additional data analysis

Although the data analysis results show that Information Quality, System Quality and Service Quality affect Net Benefits through User Satisfaction (Mediator) (Table 6 and Figure 5), this research attempts to further validate the mediation effect by comparing proposed models with rival models, as done by previous researchers ([Singh et al., 1994](#); [Tippins and Sohi, 2003](#); [Shafi 2020](#); [Shou et al 2017](#)).

In the first step, the mediating role of User Satisfaction between Information Quality and Net Benefits was evaluated. In doing so, different models were compared to test the mediating effect. In Model 1, it was proposed that User Satisfaction completely mediates the relationship between Information Quality and Net Benefits (Complete mediation). In other words, Information Quality does not affect Net Benefits directly. Model 1 is the proposed model in this study, which will be compared with other models. Model 2 examines the direct effect of Information Quality and User Satisfaction on Net Benefits (direct model). Model 3 investigates the direct and indirect effect of Information Quality on Net Benefits (partial mediation model). This model is similar to Model 1, with the direct impact of Information Quality on Net Benefits. Lastly, Model 4 examines the impact of User Satisfaction on Net Benefits through Information Quality. In this last model, Information Quality acts as a mediator between User Satisfaction and Net Benefits.

The results indicate a better model fit ($\chi^2=55.653$, RMSEA=.057, GFI=.951, AGFI=.919, NFI=.955, TLI=.974, CFI=.981) than rival models. There is strong evidence regarding the complete mediating role of user satisfaction between information quality and net benefits. That is, the information quality affects net benefits through user satisfaction.

Similar steps were followed to ascertain the mediating role of User Satisfaction between System Quality and Net Benefits. The results also indicate a better model fit ($\chi^2 =32.779$, RMSEA=.062, GFI=.965, AGFI=.931, NFI=.972, TLI=.980, CFI=.987) than rival models. Particularly, the system quality affects net benefits through user satisfaction.

Likewise, the results for examining the mediating role of user satisfaction between service Quality and Net Benefits also indicated a better model fit ($\chi^2 =86.908$, RMSEA=.051, GFI=.933, AGFI=.913,

NFI=.939, TLI=.957, CFI=.964) than rival models. In other words, service quality also affects net benefits through user satisfaction.

5.1 Discussion

Although numerous research scholars have researched the success of several information systems based on DeLone and McLean's updated model, no research has been conducted to examine the success of a Homeopathic Expert System. This study empirically examined the success of the Homeopathic Expert System in Pakistan based on McLean and DeLone model of information success.

The findings indicate that information quality, system quality, and service quality positively and significantly affect user satisfaction that is in line with the findings of previous studies ([Jen-Her Wu and Yu-Min Wang, 2006](#)). Similarly, [Petter et al. \(2008\)](#) and [Petter et al. \(2013\)](#) also concluded that Information system quality measured in terms of information quality, system quality, and service quality significantly and positively affect user satisfaction and, after that, net benefits. This indicates that all three factors are very imperative for the satisfaction of users of Homeopathic Expert Systems.

From these results, it can be inferred that users of homeopathic expert systems expect that their systems must be of high quality and provide high-quality information and services along with significant user benefits ([Wu and Wang, 2006](#); [Petter et al., 2008](#); and [Petter et al., 2013](#)). These results also reveal that Homeopathic Expert Systems are working accurately. Additionally, 73% of the participating Homeopathic expert system users, in their response to a question related to patient's satisfaction from Expert System suggested treatment, reported that patients are highly satisfied with the treatment indicated through the expert system. In other words, [DeLone and McLean \(2003\)](#) confirm that increased user satisfaction provides substantial benefits to the users, particularly, in terms of task productivity, customer satisfaction, and management control.

5.2 Theoretical and practical implications

The thesis makes significant theoretical contributions. Primarily, this research offers an example of evaluating Expert Systems (Homeopathic). The current study also empirically validated the DeLone and McLean model in the

context of homeopathic expert system. Further, this thesis also discussed the significant factors contributing to the success of a Homeopathic Expert System. Notably, this study shows that information quality, system quality, and service quality are crucial factors that significantly affect user satisfaction. The findings further show that user satisfaction is also very substantial to achieve net benefits. Most importantly, the current research is the first of its kind in Pakistan; before this research, no study was conducted in Pakistan that focuses on the evaluation of Expert Systems (Homeopathic).

This research explores the benefits of using Homeopathic Expert Systems for selecting proper medicines for homeopaths, which will help in better understanding the way of homeopathic treatment. The current research will help find out the lacunas in the existing expert systems being used in Sindh Province and provide its solutions to enable Homeopathic Doctors to provide better treatment to the patients. The present study will not only be beneficial for the researchers and Homeopathic Doctors but will also be beneficial for the Software Engineers who are interested in the field of expert systems related to the medical or Homeopathic field to fill the gap and improve the lacunas in the existing expert systems of homeopathy. The results derived from this study will be very fruitful to enhance the systems and also provide feedback to develop other expert systems. Further, the findings emanating from this study are very useful for researchers and practitioners. The research scholars can be benefited from applying successful information system models to similar research in the context of other organizations. This study filled some crucial literature gaps. The research findings also revealed that the power of information quality and system quality for predicting user satisfaction proposes that these factors are very important in the diagnostic framework for analyzing system characteristics that may lead to user satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The practitioners can apply the findings emanating from the current research with higher confidence to test the usability of expert systems at the time of designing IS. The main focus should be to improve the quality of information, followed by improving the quality of systems and services. Moreover, the findings of current research offer a better understanding and help enterprises encourage customers and users to focus on the use of expert

systems. Researchers can use these findings to look for future research on end-user satisfaction.

5.3 Conclusion

Many homeopathic expert systems are in use by different homeopaths. However, to what extent these expert systems (Homeopathy) are working accurately is relatively unknown and to what extent the users (homeopathic doctors) are satisfied with these expert systems' performance is also not known. This study was aimed to fill these literature gaps.

This research empirically finds that all independent variables significantly contribute to predicting the dependent variables. Overall, the findings emanating from this thesis offer complete support to the DeLone-McLean model as a predictive model. The improvement in the information system by increasing the quality variables (i.e., information quality, system quality, and service quality), users' satisfaction can be significantly improved, which leads to achieving net benefits in terms of task productivity, customer satisfaction, and management control. In other words, the proposed model empirically provided evidence that it can be used as a systematic tool for Homeopathic doctors to evaluate the implementation of a homeopathic expert system. The findings further reveal that Homeopathic Expert Systems are working accurately and the treatment suggested through these systems is appropriate. Additionally, most participating users also believe that patients are also satisfied with the treatment suggested by these expert systems. The findings also indicate that user satisfaction benefits users in terms of task productivity, customer satisfaction, and management control.

The research was contextualized by adopting the DeLone and McLean's model to assess the success of the Homeopathic Expert Systems. Even though this study provided important theoretical and practical implications, as in any study, some limitations offer room for further research. Further, it is suggested that similar research may be conducted in a different cultural context because the user's perceptions and expectations may differ across different cultures.

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